

THE IMPORTANCE OF FOLK ORAL CREATIVE WORKS IN EDUCATING STUDENTS IN THE SPIRIT OF MORALITY AND ENLIGHTENMENT

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Annotation

Many researchers have conducted various studies on the importance of educating students in the spirit of morality and enlightenment. Issues such as youth education, modernization of the education sector, and aesthetic upbringing through the means of art have been regularly emphasized by our President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, and important tasks in this area have been assigned to specialists of the field.

This article scientifically and theoretically substantiates the role of using samples of folk oral creativity in educating students in the spirit of morality and enlightenment and develops methodological recommendations directed toward the process.

Keywords: moral and educational spirit, aesthetic education, folk oral creativity, modernization, family, competence, creativity.

The upbringing of the younger generation and its results serve both social and personal interests. Good upbringing not only brings joy, happiness, spiritual and economic wealth to the family but also has great socio-political and moral significance for society as a whole.

When we pay attention to the national and traditional education system, every teacher or parent, in the process of educating their child or student, teaches them to be creative, to generate new ideas, and to approach every social situation with a new perspective and understanding. This approach is considered the fundamental basis of every field or sector.

As we know, each country provides education and upbringing to the younger generation in accordance with its own mentality and social context, integrating it into its educational system. In our country, the application of international experience in developing personal creativity and competence began during the years of independence. Competence and creativity represent the student youth's mastery of a

particular field and their creative pursuit of goals, directly contributing to the crucial task of nurturing creative individuals.

Developing students' creativity is a guarantee of the country's intellectual wealth, and the cultivation of creative personalities to enhance the divergent thinking of youth is one of the main issues of modern pedagogy.

Educating young students as qualified professionals and humanistic individuals who understand the essence of social, economic, political, moral, and cultural processes carried out in strengthening our country's independence is impossible without turning to samples of folk oral creativity.

In organizing various meetings, roundtable discussions, and debate evenings among university students, it is necessary to cite examples from folk oral creativity that reflect our national mentality and contribute to the spiritual growth of students. It is also essential to prepare, publish, and distribute scientific, methodological, and practical literature and manuals related to the moral and educational development of students, as well as provide access to educationally valuable literature.

At present, the tendency to consider immorality as culture, and conversely, to disregard genuine moral values by viewing folk oral creativity as a remnant of the past, poses a serious threat to today's progress, human life, family sanctity, and youth education. Many are now realizing how important it is to combat such challenges spreading across the world like a calamity. Therefore, in organizing educational and awareness-raising events among youth, it is essential to use folk oral works to strengthen national self-awareness, prevent the influence of alien ideologies, and implement effective preventive measures.

The upbringing of youth begins, first and foremost, within the family. Especially in the Uzbek family environment, qualities such as kindness, mutual respect, devotion to parental duties, and love for the Motherland are nurtured. To raise a well-rounded individual, parents must be knowledgeable, and possess moral, political, and legal awareness. It is within the family that a child develops their spiritual world, forms basic concepts of good and evil, and begins to express positive or negative opinions about events occurring around them. Therefore, parents should guide their children properly through their own knowledge and example, shaping positive thinking and instilling appropriate attitudes toward good and bad behavior — all of which can be achieved only through upbringing.

It should be especially noted that in no other country in the world is there as much attention to the institution of the community as in our nation. Consequently, fostering cooperation in upbringing and studying as well as promoting relevant experiences are among the most urgent tasks of today.

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